

Lactic acid bacteria used to produce natural flavour compounds from whey and castor oil

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Abstract

Whey and castor oil are economic raw materials and can be used as nutrients to produce molecules of interest by fermentation with lactic acid bacteria. In this study, aromatic compounds produced by the bacteria *Lactobacillus plantarum* A6 and *Lactococcus lactis cremoris* were investigated in the fermentation of whey with two concentrations of castor oil (3 % and 6 %), using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) with solid-phase microextraction (SPME). The results showed the production of aromatic compounds, mainly: Hydroxyacetone, Acetic acid, Formic acid, γ -Butyrolactone, 2(5H)-furanone, Furanol, Furfural, Furfuryl alcohol, Dihydroxyacetone and Pentanal. Both microorganisms managed to metabolize the fatty acids from castor oil; however, the concentration of castor oil did not have a significant effect on the production of flavours ($p > 0.05$). On the other hand, significant differences were found according to the type of microorganism ($p < 0.05$), obtaining a different aromatic profile for each lactic acid bacteria. Finally, the flavour profile was described as pungent, sharp, fruity, creamy, buttery, sweet, alcoholic, and fermented, thus achieving an interesting aromatic base to be used in natural flavours.

Keywords: lactic acid bacteria, whey, castor oil, fermentation, natural flavour

Introduction

Whey is considered a by-product of the dairy industry and is classified as a water and soil pollutant, due to its high chemical and biochemical oxygen demand [1]. Both whey and castor oil are economic raw materials and can be used as nutrients to produce molecules of interest by fermentation with lactic acid bacteria, which are known to produce aromatic compounds in different foods [2, 3]. Fermentation has emerged as a promising technology for producing natural molecules for use in flavours, creating the need to search for new strains and substrates to produce natural aromatic compounds. Consequently, the objective of this study was to investigate and characterize the aromatic compounds produced by fermentation of whey and castor oil (CO) with the bacteria *Lactobacillus plantarum* A6 (Lp) and *Lactococcus lactis cremoris* (Ll). For this, a liquid fermentation was carried out, the aromatic compounds were analysed using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and the treatments were discriminated against through a principal component analysis (PCA), evidencing the aromatic molecules generated.

Experimental

The microorganisms used were obtained from the laboratory of microbiology and applied biotechnology (MIBIA) Cali - Colombia, were reactivated and cultivated in medium MRS until use. Analysis of fermented assays was carried out using gas chromatography (Agilent Technologies, GC 7890B) with mass spectrometry (Agilent Technologies, 5977A) (GC-MS), the tests were sampled by SPME (Solid Phase Microextraction) with a DVB/CAR/PDMS fibre. The column used was a Thermo TG-1MS (30 m x 0.25 mm internal diameter, 1 μ m film thickness). The injection port was maintained at 250 °C for a 6 min desorption time. The GC oven was programmed from 60 °C to 280 °C with a temperature ramp of 4 °C/min. The injection mode was split (5:1), high purity helium was used as carrier gas at a flow of 1.5 mL/min. The quadrupole MS detector was maintained at 230 °C with an ionisation energy of 70 eV. Mass spectra were compared with the NIST library using the Agilent MassHunter Unknowns Analysis program, and the peak area of each volatile was obtained and calculated using the normalization technique.

Fermentation

The fermentation was carried out in Erlenmeyer flasks with 100 mL culture medium, which consisted of 11.4 % whey, 3 % or 6 % castor oil, 10 % bacteria inoculum with 24 h of previous incubation in MRS medium, and water (72.6 – 75.6 %). The assays were fermented for 48 h at 35 °C. The trials were performed triplicate for each treatment. After the fermentation, 300 μ L were sampled and analysed by GC-MS.

Statistical design and analysis

A two-factor design was performed with three levels; microorganism type: without microorganism (control), *Lactobacillus plantarum* A6 (Lp) and *Lactococcus lactis cremoris* (LI); and amount of castor oil: oil-free (CO0), 3% (CO3), and 6% (CO6). A heat map was made to visualize the aromatic production of each treatment and a Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed to discriminate the molecules produced for each treatment, the analysis was carried out in the XLSTAT statistic program. The factorial design was carried out with the MINITAB 2018 program, to analyse the effects of the factors for each aromatic molecule. Analyses were performed with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

Results and discussion

Changes in the aromatic profile according to the treatment evaluated during fermentation can be seen in Figure 1. Regarding the control without fermentation, a natural increase in the production of acetic acid, formic acid, and furfuryl alcohol, all molecules characteristic of the metabolism of lactic acid bacteria, can be seen for both Lp and LI. In addition, it is observed that the control has a profile of fatty acids and molecules from castor oil, which were not found in fermented treatments, indicating the metabolization and transformation of the above-mentioned compounds.

Figure 1: Heatmap representing the production of different aromatic molecules analysed by GC-MS. The horizontal axis shows the different treatments with *L. plantarum* (Lp), *L. lactis* (LI), and control without microorganism, with different amounts of castor oil 0 % (0CO), 3 % (3CO), and 6 % (6CO). The colour bar represents the relative percentage of peak areas obtained by SPME.

For some molecules (furfuryl alcohol, 2-pentylfuran, 2(5H)-furanone, pentanal, and methyl 2-furoate), the concentration of castor oil did not have a significant effect ($p > 0.05$), therefore, the generation of those molecules is not related to the transformation of the oil, and are probably generated by the action of the whey consumption. The main molecules produced were furfuryl alcohol, acetic acid, formic acid, 5-hydroxymethyl furfural, and dihydroxyacetone. Also, some molecules with less concentration were detected, such as hydroxyacetone, γ -butyrolactone, furaneol, pentanal, and 2-pentylfuran. The aromatic profile of the produced compounds was described as pungent, sharp, fruity, creamy, buttery, sweet, alcoholic, and fermented, so it can be used to formulate flavours with these characteristics.

As shown in Figure 2, principal component analysis allows to classify the treatments for both microorganisms. With both microorganisms, the treatments were assorted by the production of aromatic molecules, with two main components representing 96.9 % of the data for the treatments. Mainly, it is observed that both microorganisms

Figure 2: Principal component analysis (PCA) discriminating the molecules produced for each fermentation treatment used, A) with the control treatment, and B) with only the fermentation treatments. Components represent A) 96.9 % and B) 98.55 % of the analysed data. LL represents the treatments with *L. lactis* and LP with *L. plantarum*. 0CO, 3CO, and 6CO, represent the castor oil (CO) concentrations (0%, 3%, and 6%), and control treatment represents the unfermented treatment. Molecules are discriminated in quadrants representing their chemical origin (triangles for quadrant one primary metabolites, filled circles for quadrant two secondary metabolites, empty circles in quadrant three, and rhombus for quadrant four).

managed to produce similar molecules, and all the castor oil concentration treatments had no effect on the generation of differences in the aromatic profile. However, the control was discriminated against with molecules with a fat profile, because of the oil present in the unfermented treatment

Figure 2B, representing 98.55 % of the data, shows the discriminative analysis of treatments without the inclusion of the unfermented control. Variability are well represented in the analysis, where the first component PC1 represents 95.62 % of the total variance of data. In this analysis it can be seen that primary molecules of major metabolites, such as acetic acid and formic acid, are discriminated in quadrant one, the treatments were discriminated between microorganisms, and it can be observed that the concentration of castor oil had a significant effect at 6 % with the strain *L. plantarum*. This effect is not so significant in the treatments with *L. lactis*. It can also be seen that secondary metabolites are classified in the quadrant opposite to treatments, showing that there is no direct relationship in their production, regardless of the type of microorganism and the amount of substrate, and may be favoured by fermentation conditions.

Fermentations can be subjected to optimization of biotechnological parameters, to increase the generation of certain molecules using different substrates, or even new strains of lactic acid bacteria. This study managed to demonstrate the possibility of using whey as a raw material for biotechnological processes, and in this way, reduce its negative effect on the environment through its fermentation and use to generate added value.

Conclusion

Fermentation of whey and castor oil with the use of lactic acid bacteria proved to be a promising treatment to produce aromatic compounds. The analysis using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) with solid-phase microextraction (SPME) was able to identify the production of several compounds, and the principal component analysis (PCA) allowed to discriminate the treatments, and observe the effect of fermentation in the generation of some compounds. Finally, this work is a contribution to the investigation in the use of new sources of substrates to generate flavour compounds, which implies the need to continue this type of studies, to achieve interesting aromatic bases to be used in natural flavours.

References

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